

ELECTRICAL ENERGY SAVING IN INDUSTRY

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Abstract: Nowadays, the efficient use of energy resources is given great importance in all countries of the world. Such a situation can be explained by the increase in investment expenditure for the extraction and processing of fuel and energy resources, the increase in the consumption of additional labor resources and materials. This article provides information about the electricity industry and energy efficiency.

Key words: Energy saving, electric welding, direct current, battery.

Achieving energy savings when using cranes Cranes are the machines that consume the most energy when moving a load from one place to another. Cranes serve to move materials and goods from one place to another in both horizontal and vertical directions. In the construction of industrial and civil facilities, the tower type of cranes is widely used, and their load capacity ranges from several tons to several tens of tons. The motors of these cranes are mainly asynchronous motors 4MT msum (power 2.2 - 200 kW), MTF and MTN (phase rotor) and MTKF, MTKN (rotor short-circuited, power 1.4 - 30 kW) and type D constant current motors (capacity 2.5 - 185 kW). Also, bridge types are widely used in metallurgical and machine-building enterprises, their load-carrying capacity ranges from several tons to hundreds of tons.

The waste of electrical energy that occurs in the electrical operations of crane mechanisms depends on the type of adjustable electrical equipment used. The ratio

of the electric energy used for useful production in a certain period of time to the total electric energy consumption of the electric system is called the equivalent FIK - 3 of the system. T_{j3} varies depending on the ratio of the number of starts to Z in the specified time period. As can be seen from the graph, thyristor-controlled DC converters are the highest in electric drives, but if we take into account the somewhat complicated operation of DC motors, then this does not justify itself.

Achieving energy savings during the use of conveyors and pumps In construction, mining and other industries, belt conveyors are widely used to move loose, granular and lumpy materials horizontally and at an angle from one place to another. These devices mainly use 4A three-phase rotor short-circuited and phase rotor asynchronous motors, the connection power reaches several hundred kW. In multi-speed conveyors, asynchronous motors with high starting torque are used in conveyors with high slip or phase rotor, in heavy production mode.

In order to save electricity in pumping equipment, the following should be implemented:

1. It is necessary to increase the load of the pumps, taking into account that the minimum comparative value of electricity corresponds to the maximum load of the pumps. If the description of the water conduit does not correspond to the parameters of the pump passport, the pump must be replaced.

2. Low efficiency pumps should be replaced with high efficiency and high FIK

Energy-saving operation modes of compressors and fans are widely used in all areas of compressed air production. For example, compressed air is used in concrete breakers, power hammers, sanders and vibrators, paint remote control and paint sprayers used in the construction of industrial and civil buildings. Compressed air is produced in compressors. Motoring power in compressors can range from several hundred watts to several thousand kilowatts. Compressors with a synchronous motor with a power of thousands of kilowatts are used for the transportation of large volumes of gaseous media.

It is advisable to take the following measures to reduce the consumption of electricity in the compressor's electrical operations:

Heating the compressed air and using thermal insulation in the air duct reduces air waste, which in itself reduces electricity consumption. In this case, the electricity saving is calculated by the following formula: $A \xi = 0.22Q A T$ of, where Q is the amount of compressed air, m^3/min , $A T$ is the heat insulation device installed in the air duct and after the device o temperature difference in the conductor (average value during the year), $^{\circ}C$, (electrical energy consumed for obtaining 0 - 1 m^3 of compressed air, $kW*s/ m^3$, t - time of operation of the computer during the year, hours.

Saving electricity in electric welding devices Electric welding method is widely used when welding metal structures together. Electric welding is performed on alternating current and constant current welding devices. Electric welding is performed at low voltage and high current values.

In order to use electricity efficiently when carrying out welding work, the following must be observed:

-Welding should be carried out from direct current welding devices to alternating current welding devices. DC welding devices are used only when the requirements for welding joints are high and automation of the welding process is necessary. A stick arc welder consumes 2.9 kWh of electricity to melt 1 kg of metal, and an automatic or semi-automatic welding device consumes 2.0 kWh of electricity. AC welding equipment has a high FIK, is easy to use, and the equipment is relatively inexpensive.

-Automation is necessary in cases where stick welding is possible. Automatic welding devices reduce electricity consumption by 30-40%. Changing stick welding to point (contact) welding, although it leads to a change in technology, electricity consumption is reduced by 2 - 2.5 times, when switching to the contact welding method, electricity consumption is reduced by 15%. The use of semi-automatic and automatic welding devices operating in constant current reduces electricity consumption by up to 40%.

Saving electricity in transport Reducing energy consumption in electric cars and increasing the efficiency of the connection is an urgent issue in our current development. Electric cars are occupying their place in transport, slightly displacing cars running on organic fuel.

It is necessary to technically improve the electric cars traveling inside and outside the city. The most practical issue is that electric cars driving outside the city at a speed of 80 - 100 km/h can cover a distance of at least 160 km with a single charge of their batteries. To do this, reduce total road resistance and electric car power loss from auxiliary connections; it is achieved by increasing the FIK of accumulator batteries, electric motors, electric vehicle transmission and communication devices and power cables.

The main issue here should be to reduce energy consumption in overcoming total road resistance and reduce power loss in auxiliary equipment and improve the braking system. The drag coefficient for electric cars should not exceed 0.2 - 0.3, which is a difficult but solvable issue. Using regenerative braking in braking is the most desirable task from the point of view of energy saving. In recuperative braking, all the kinetic energy of the electric car is converted into electrical energy and returned to the battery cells. Although various types of batteries for individual electric cars are currently being developed, lead-acid batteries are the ones that are actually used in electric cars. The mass of the cable is almost equal to the mass of electric cars. Therefore, reducing the mass of the ulaming remains an urgent constructive problem. The use of direct current motors with a series drive in electric cars has several advantages over the use of other types of electric motors. Because in this type of electric motors, it is possible to generate a torque equal to the required values at low speed values, and it is also possible to generate a small required torque at high speeds. It is easy to control and can be connected to the right battery pack. The FIC of fuel cells currently being developed is higher than 35% (if the waste heat in the fuel cell operating system is reused with a heat pump, the total FIC of the power plant can reach 94%). In the future, there are opportunities to use other types of fuels for fuel cells. Due to the fact that the use of lead-acid batteries in electric

cars does not fully meet the requirements for electric transport, research is being conducted on the production of fundamentally new types of batteries. A promising battery for future use in electric vehicles is currently the sulfur-sodium battery. A solid electrolyte is located between the cathode - liquid sodium and liquid sulfur - anode. The electrolyte acts as a filter that only passes sodium ions. Sodium ions react with sulfur and a potential difference is formed between the electrolytes. The final product sodium polysulfite is formed only when the electric motor is running, i.e. when the current passes through the electric circuit.

The results of the conducted road research show that an electric van with a sulfur-sodium battery can travel 96-120 km depending on the condition of the road and traffic conditions with a single charge of the battery. At present, the energy capacity of a separate element of a sulfur battery has been increased to 550 W*h. 90 of these battery cells are enough to supply the electric motor with electricity

In the USA, Japan, Germany and France, which are leaders in the automobile industry, electric cars using a hybrid motor, i.e., a combination of a gasoline engine and an electric motor, are being tested.

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